

ADSORPTIVE PROPERTIES OF SYNTHETIC RESINS.

PART III.

BY S. S. BHATNAGAR, A. N. KAPUR AND MAHENDRA SARUP BHATNAGAR.

The adsorption of a homologous series of mono- and dibasic aliphatic acids by acid and alkali-condensed phenolic resins and by an amino-resin has been studied. In acid-condensed phenolic resins, the adsorption in a homologous series increases with increase in molecular weight, while in alkali-catalysed phenolic resins and amino-resins the order of adsorption is reversed. The adsorption of substituted acetic acids by an amino-resin has also been determined and the influence of the various substituents on adsorption studied. The introduction of acidic groups increases adsorption, while that of basic groups decreases it. The effect of the amino group is much more pronounced than that of hydroxyl group.

In a previous paper from this laboratory Bhatnagar, Kapur and Puri (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 679) carried out a quantitative study of the adsorption of non- or weakly dissociated substances by acid-catalysed phenolic resins. They found that the removal of dissolved substances from solution by the resins followed the ordinary laws of adsorption and that in an acid-condensed phenolic resin, the adsorption of organic acids in a homologous series increased strongly and regularly with the increase of molecular weight. Tsuruta (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind. Japan*, 1938, **41**, 129B). studied the sorption of homologous series of fatty acids on an ammonia-condensed phenolic resin and though he obtained results similar to those of Bhatnagar, Kapur and Puri (*loc. cit.*), he found that the amount of sorption decreased with increase in molecular weight.

This anomaly was ascribed by him to the probable presence of traces of ammonia in the adsorbed state in the resin. Though the presence of traces of impurities may lead to increased or diminished general adsorption, it did not appear probable that they could have been responsible for the reversal of the order of adsorption. It appeared more likely that the reversal of the Traube's rule resulted from the differences in the internal structure of the resin. Such reversals are known to occur in the case of activated carbon. Dubinin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, **140A**, 81 ; 1930, **150A**, 145) has shown that the less highly activated charcoals possess very fine ultrapores, while the more highly activated charcoals possess larger pores. The finer pores in the former allow the smaller sorbate molecules to penetrate, but are too small for the larger sorbate molecules and thus bring about a reversal of the order.

In view of the above, it was considered necessary to repeat our own as well as Tsuruta's results. Further, the adsorptive properties of basic resins have been studied at length with respect to a large number of substituted aliphatic acids with a view to throw more light on the mechanism of adsorption in synthetic resins.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Resins.

(i) *Acid-condensed Resin.*—The resin was prepared in the manner described in the previous paper.

(ii) *Ammonia-condensed Resin.*—Equal parts by weight of phenol and formalin (40%) were agitated for an hour in a separating funnel in presence of 5% on the weight of phenol of strong ammonia. A viscous, oily layer of the resin was formed. It was drawn off, washed with water till the filtrate was free from traces of ammonia. The resin, which was in the liquid state, was heated at a temperature ranging from 98° to 100° till it became solid. The solid was finely powdered and passed through a 60 mesh sieve. A large sample of the resin was prepared in the above manner and used throughout all studies.

(iii) *Basic Resins.*—The resin was prepared by dissolving 1 part of *m*-phenylenediamine in 10 parts of dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1). To the clear solution 5 parts of formalin (40%) were added. A dark brown resin was precipitated in about five minutes. The resin was filtered, heated at 100° in presence of excess of hydrochloric acid to render it insoluble in water, and washed with hot water to remove all impurities. The resin was dried, finely powdered and passed through a 60 mesh sieve.

Adsorption Experiments.

The adsorption experiments were carried out in stoppered glass bottles which were thoroughly cleaned, steamed and dried. The powdered resin (1 g.) was weighed out in each bottle and 100 c. c. of the aqueous solutions of the acids were run in. The bottles were vigorously shaken and set aside for 36 hours to attain equilibrium. The supernatant solution (10 c. c.) was pipetted out and run into excess of standard sodium hydroxide solution. The equilibrium concentration (C_e , in millimoles per litre) was determined by titrating the excess of caustic soda against standard hydrochloric acid. Blank experiments were run side by side which gave the original concentration (C_0 , in millimoles per litre). The difference ($C_0 - C_e$) gave the amount adsorbed (x , in millimoles per g. of the resin) from 100 c. c. of the aqueous solutions.

Adsorption in a Homologous Series of Aliphatic Acids.

The results for the adsorption of formic, acetic and butyric acids by acid- and ammonia-catalysed phenol-formaldehyde resins are given in Tables I and II respectively.

TABLE I.

Fatty acids.

Sorption of acids by 1 g. of phenol-formaldehyde resin (acid-catalysed) from 100 c.c. of aqueous solution.

Acid.	C_0 .	C_e .	x .	% Adsorption.
Formic	10.000	9.800	0.200	2.0
	9.040	8.850	0.190	2.1
	8.030	7.850	0.180	2.2
	5.000	4.860	0.140	2.8
Acetic	10.000	9.500	0.500	5.0
	9.058	8.600	0.458	5.55
	8.040	7.600	0.440	5.47
	7.206	6.800	0.406	5.7
Butyric	10.000	9.100	0.900	9.0
	8.950	8.10	0.850	9.5
	8.000	7.20	0.800	10.0
	7.050	6.30	0.750	10.6

TABLE II.

Fatty acids.

Sorption of acids by 1 g. of phenol-formaldehyde resin (ammonia-catalysed) from 100 c.c. of their aqueous solution.

Acid.	C_0 .	C_e .	x .	% Adsorption.
Formic	10.000	7.300	2.700	27.00
	9.100	6.530	2.570	28.23
	8.000	5.650	2.350	29.28
	7.000	4.800	2.200	31.42
Acetic	10.000	7.700	2.300	23.00
	9.100	6.900	2.200	24.17
	7.900	5.900	2.000	25.31
	7.000	5.150	1.850	26.42
Butyric	10.000	8.600	1.400	14.00
	8.900	7.600	1.300	14.61
	8.360	7.100	1.260	15.07
	7.030	6.100	1.150	15.80

It is clear from Table I that in acid-catalysed resin, the adsorption in a homologous series increases with increase in the molecular weight which is in accord with the previous observation of Bhatnagar, Kapur and Pur (*loc. cit.*). Table II shows that, as already reported by Tsuruta, the order of adsorption is reversed in ammonia-catalysed resins.

TABLE III.

Sorption by 1 g. of resorcinol-formaldehyde resin from 100 c.c. of the solution.

	Acid-catalysed resin.				Ammonia-catalysed resin.			
	C ₀ .	C _e .	x.	% Adsorption.	C ₀ .	C _e .	x.	% Adsorption.
Formic	10.00	9.70	0.3	3.3	10.0	6.3	3.7	37.0
Acetic	10.00	9.30	0.7	7.0	10.0	7.0	3.0	30.0
Butyric	10.00	8.70	1.3	13.0	10.0	8.0	2.0	20.0

From Table III we again observe that the normal order of adsorption holds in the case of acid- and reverse order in alkali-catalysed resorcinol-formaldehyde resins. It appeared improbable that the adsorbed traces of ammonia or other impurities could be responsible, as suggested by Tsuruta, for the reversal of the order of adsorption. The ammonia-condensed resin was, therefore, refluxed with hydrochloric acid for two hours with constant stirring to ensure complete removal of adsorbed ammonia. The resin after having been washed free of hydrochloric acid, dried, powdered and sieved still showed the same order of adsorption with the difference that there was a general decrease in the amounts adsorbed. This experiment clearly showed that the reversal of the order of adsorption could not have been due to the presence of traces of ammonia as impurity. It is more likely that the reversal is due to the difference in the internal structure of the acid- and ammonia-condensed resins. It is well known that ammonia and alkalis in general are more powerful condensing agents than hydrochloric acid. The alkali-condensed resins are, therefore, more highly polymerised and possess very fine ultrapores, while acid-condensed resins possess larger pores. This would explain the reversal of the order of adsorption, since the smaller sorbate molecules can penetrate the ultrapores, which are too small for the larger sorbate molecules. Similar explanation for the observance of Traube's rule and its reversal in various activated charcoals was given by Dubinin. It will

be seen from Tables I, II and III that the ammonia condensed resins invariably show much greater adsorption than the acid-condensed resins.

TABLE IV.

Monobasic acids.

Sorption of acids by 1 g. of *m*-phenylenediamine resin from 100 c.c. of their aqueous solutions.

Acids.	C_0 .	C_e .	x .	% Adsorption.
Formic	10.050	5.981	4.069	40.37
	9.346	5.320	4.026	43.00
	8.223	4.299	3.924	47.73
	7.476	3.645	3.831	51.25
Acetic	10.090	6.354	3.736	37.04
	9.030	5.467	3.563	38.45
	8.037	4.673	3.364	41.86
	7.010	3.832	3.178	45.33
Butyric	10.000	7.196	2.804	28.04
	8.738	6.120	2.618	30.00
	7.943	5.467	2.476	31.17
	7.010	4.673	2.337	33.33

TABLE V.

Dibasic acids.

Sorption of acids by 1 g. of *m*-phenylenediamine resin from 100 c.c. of their aqueous solutions.

Acids.	C_0 .	C_e .	x .	% Adsorption.
Oxalic	9.9060	1.1215	8.7845	88.68
	8.9730	0.9346	8.0384	89.58
	7.8500	0.7476	7.1024	90.48
	7.0100	0.6074	6.4026	91.33
Malonic	10.090	1.402	8.688	86.11
	8.925	1.028	7.897	88.48
	8.409	0.8879	7.5211	89.44
	7.523	0.6541	6.8689	91.30
Succinic	11.400	2.990	8.410	73.77
	9.438	2.336	7.102	75.25
	8.223	1.865	6.358	77.27
	7.290	1.588	5.702	78.20
Adipic	10.230	3.083	7.147	70.14
	9.159	2.523	6.636	72.45
	8.178	2.055	6.123	74.86
	7.296	1.682	5.608	76.92

Similarly if we consider the adsorption of acids by basic resins. (Tables IV- and V), we find that the amount of adsorption is much greater than either in acid- or in alkali-catalysed phenolic resins. Again we notice that the order of adsorption is the same as in the case of alkali-catalysed phenolic resins *i.e.* inverse to that of the normal Traube rule. It appears that the adsorption of acids by synthetic resins is governed by two factors (*a*) surface forces and (*b*) forces resulting from physicochemical action of hydrogen ions with basic groups. The adsorption of fatty acids by acid-condensed phenolic resins is a physical phenomenon and the order of adsorption can be qualitatively accounted for on the Gibbs-Thompson law.

TABLE VI.

Influence of ionisation on adsorption.

Acids.	% Adsorption from 0.01M solutions.		Ionisation constant at 25°C.
	Phenolic resin (NH ₃ condensed).	<i>m</i> -Phenylene-diamine resin.	
Formic	27.00	40.47	2.14×10^{-4}
Acetic	23.00	37.04	1.86×10^{-5}
Butyric	14.00	24.04	1.48×10^{-5}
Oxalic	60.0	88.68	3.8×10^{-2}
Malonic	46.5	86.11	1.61×10^{-3}
Succinic	38.0	73.77	6.6×10^{-5}
Adipic	21.0	70.14	3.7×10^{-6}

In the case of alkali-condensed phenolic and amino-resins, both physical and chemical forces came into play, the latter masking the effect of the former; the absorbate molecules penetrate the capillary structure of the resin depending on the interfacial tension relationships and their accommodability in the capillary structure of the resin. Further, from Table VI it will be seen that the adsorption in a homologous series is greater, the greater the ionisation constant of the acid. This clearly shows that in the case of amino or basic resins, the adsorption is primarily chemical depending on the interaction of the hydrogen ions with the basic groups in the resin, the stronger acids showing greater adsorption than comparatively weak ones.

TABLE VII.

Influence of substituents on adsorption.

Sorption of substituted acetic acids by 1 g. of *m*-phenylenediamine resin from 100 c. c. of their aqueous solutions.

Acids.	C_0 .	C_e .	x .	% Adsorption
Acetic	10.090	6.354	3.736	37.04
	9.030	5.467	3.563	39.45
	8.037	4.673	3.364	41.86
	7.010	3.832	3.178	45.33
Chloracetic	10.50	4.10	6.40	60.95
	9.60	3.60	6.00	62.50
	8.35	2.90	5.45	65.27
	7.35	2.40	4.95	67.35
Dichloracetic	10.50	2.40	8.10	77.14
	9.40	2.00	7.40	78.72
	8.40	1.60	6.80	79.00
	7.30	1.35	5.95	81.50
Trichloracetic	10.00	1.60	8.40	84.00
	9.00	1.40	7.60	84.44
	8.10	1.20	6.90	85.18
	7.05	1.00	6.05	85.81
Phenylacetic	10.00	2.70	7.30	73.00
	9.00	2.30	6.70	74.44
	8.30	2.00	6.30	76.00
	7.00	1.50	5.50	78.57
Cyanacetic	10.40	3.50	6.90	66.34
	9.50	3.00	6.50	68.42
	8.30	2.40	5.90	71.08
	7.30	1.90	5.40	73.97
Aminoacetic	12.00	11.00	1.00	8.33
	7.00	6.25	0.75	10.70
	5.35	4.70	0.65	12.10
	3.90	3.35	0.55	14.10
Hydroxyacetic	10.4	7.2	3.20	30.8
	9.2	6.1	3.10	33.7
	8.1	5.1	3.00	37.3
	7.1	4.2	2.90	40.8

The adsorption of acetic, mono-, di- and tri-, phenyl-, cyano-, amino- and hydroxyacetic acids by *m*-phenylenediamine resin has been determined and the results are recorded in Table VII. It will be seen from the table that the introduction of acidic groups increases adsorption, while that of basic groups decreases it. Further, the effect of the amino group in lowering the adsorption is much more pronounced than that of the hydroxyl group, due probably to the former being more basic than the latter. Similar results were also obtained by Bartell and Miller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 15, 1106) who showed that the introduction of the hydroxyl or amino group in an organic acid decreased adsorption on carbon to an extent depending on the nature of the acid.

TABLE VIII.

Influence of ionisation on adsorption.

Acids.	% Adsorption from 0.01M soln.	Ion. const. at 25°C.	Acids.	% Adsorption from 0.01M soln.	Ion. const. at 25°C.
Acetic	37.04	1.85×10^{-5}	Cyanacetic (nitrilmalonic acid)	66.34	3.56×10^{-3}
Chloroacetic	60.95	1.52×10^{-3}	Hydroxyacetic (glycollic acid)	30.80	1.51×10^{-4}
Dichloroacetic	77.14	5.00×10^{-2}	Aminoacetic (glycocoll)	8.33	3.4×10^{-10}
Trichloroacetic	84.00	2.00×10^{-1}			
Phenylacetic	73.00	5.45×10^{-6}			

In Table VIII are given the percentage adsorptions of the substituted acetic acids and their ionisation constants at 25°. It will be seen that here again the general relation between adsorbability and ionisation holds except in the case of hydroxyacetic acid. The influence of the hydroxyl group in depressing the adsorption is well known and in this case appears to be potent enough to overcome the increased adsorption due to a higher dissociation constant.